

VERITY Recommendations for Fostering Trust in Science

SCIENCE-SOCIETY FACILITATORS

As Stewards of Trust (SOT), **Science-Society Facilitators** engage the public in scientific initiatives and foster collaboration between scientists and society, such as civil society organisations (CSOs), science advocacy groups, and community advisory boards.

Examples: Science-Society Facilitators include civil society organisations (CSOs), science advocacy groups, citizen science networks, community advisory boards, environmental and health NGOs, and other intermediaries working to bridge the gap between research and public life.

Why trust in science matters for Science-Society Facilitators

Science-society facilitators play a crucial role in connecting research with diverse communities, yet engagement efforts often fall short of creating meaningful, equitable, and sustained relationships (Irwin, 2006). Too frequently, participatory processes are tokenistic, used to meet funding grant requirements rather than to genuinely incorporate public perspectives. This dynamic can reinforce public perceptions of science as detached from real societal needs, inaccessible and top-down, particularly among historically marginalised groups who may carry prior negative experiences with scientific or healthcare institutions (Ottinger, 2013). When participation feels instrumental rather than empowering, trust in science may erode rather than strengthen.

Practical and structural barriers further limit impact. Short-term and limited funding, inadequate institutional support, and rigid project structures often constrain facilitators' ability to design inclusive, responsive engagement strategies. Scientific institutions often lack the infrastructure, incentives, or training to support meaningful public engagement, while researchers may be hesitant to participate; at the same time, facilitators must balance openness with influence, ensuring transparency and inclusivity without allowing dominant interests to distort participation.

Power asymmetries within participatory forums risk reducing citizens to passive roles rather than co-creators of knowledge, and citizen science efforts often struggle to reach beyond organised civil society to engage underrepresented or disaffected groups. Additionally, concerns around data ethics, privacy, and representation are sometimes overlooked, diminishing the credibility of well-intentioned initiatives. Religious, ideological, or political tensions can also complicate efforts to build inclusive coalitions of trust.

How can Science-Society Facilitators foster trust in science?

To foster trust, science-society facilitators must **advance co-creative, inclusive, and sustained engagement models that move beyond consultation toward genuine collaboration**. This includes building platforms for dialogue that are accessible, diverse, and responsive to community needs, supported by adequate training, funding, and ethical safeguards. Facilitators should work to integrate local knowledge into research design, promote mutual learning, and ensure fair recognition of citizen contributions. Investing in feedback mechanisms, community partnerships, and inclusive storytelling can help **shift the perception of science as an elite endeavour to one that is collaborative, accountable, and rooted in shared values**.

Building trustworthy science

Scientific Transparency, Accessibility, and Open Science

- Develop open science guidelines that are field-specific, inclusive, clear, relevant, and accessible to the general public and marginalised groups (including those with lower educational attainment, economically vulnerable individuals, and older adults).

Public Engagement, Inclusivity and Benefit Sharing

- Demonstrate and communicate real-world benefits of science in everyday life.
- Raise awareness about the importance of both basic and applied science in meeting societal goals and addressing societal challenges.
- Engage communities throughout research processes to respect local knowledge, embrace diverse perspectives, and embed values such as fairness, respect, care, and honesty into practices to address societal needs.
- Foster co-creative approaches and address power dynamics to strengthen inclusive collaboration among all stakeholders, including scientists and citizens within the ecosystem of trust in science.

Engaging the public in scientific processes

Building Frameworks for Sustainable Engagement

- Shift from one-way deficit models of science communication towards relational approaches that foster mutual trust through dialogue and meaningful engagement.
- Break silos between mainstream research and citizen engagement by integrating the public as active contributors to research processes.

- Build inclusive engagement platforms such as citizen assemblies and participatory initiatives at all levels (the EU, national, and local) that connect researchers, citizens, policymakers, civil society, businesses, and the media.

Recognising, Funding, and Rewarding Public Engagement

- Establish fair compensation mechanisms for citizen contributions and recognise public engagement as integral to research impact.
- Advocate for inclusive authorship policies in academic publishing to credit citizen contributions.

Tailored approaches

- Make scientific processes more inclusive by actively involving marginalised and underrepresented groups (particularly those with lower educational attainment, economically vulnerable individuals, and older adults), using approaches tailored to socio-demographic factors, belief profiles, and community-specific needs.
- Identify the diverse characteristics and needs of different communities through consultative social scientific methods such as interviews and focus groups, which will provide insights for designing and implementing tailored strategies for public engagement.

Collaboration and Knowledge Sharing

- Create communities of practice that bring together researchers and citizens to share knowledge, co-develop quality standards, and identify best practices for public engagement, supported by clear guidelines, practical training, and realistic planning tools.
- Encourage scientists to incorporate local knowledge and address community-specific needs.
- Cultivate public interest in science through hands-on activities, interactive tools, and citizen co-creation projects.

Fostering Critical Thinking

- Promote critical thinking, rather than blind trust, to build resilience against mis/disinformation and mistrust.
- Combat mis/disinformation by actively engaging with the public, collaborating with civil society, and disseminating research results.

Monitoring and Sustainability

- Implement clear and consistent feedback mechanisms to ensure participants remain informed and engaged throughout and beyond the research process.
- Adapt feedback mechanisms to specific challenges of research in fragile contexts (e.g. high-risk regions or socio-economically vulnerable settings).

Educating and Raising Awareness

Public Education on Science Fundamentals

- Promote public understanding of the scientific method, including uncertainty, falsifiability, and the iterative process, to counter misconceptions and mistrust.
- Make complex scientific concepts accessible to the public without compromising accuracy.
- Promote public awareness of the economic and social benefits of science, while fostering critical thinking, informed questioning of science-based interventions, and support for responsible research and innovation.
- Offer regular refresher courses for teachers at all educational levels to keep them up to date with current scientific research and responsible research practices to support them in raising informed future citizens.

Curriculum Integration and Innovation

- Foster inquiry-based learning, emphasising theory formation, experimentation, and analysis.

Targeted and Inclusive Outreach

- Use innovative formats like science buses, cafés, and shops to reach underserved communities and remote areas.

Bridging Academia, Industry, and Public

- Encourage collaborative projects between academia, industry and civil society to enhance practical education and innovation.

Combating Mis/Disinformation Through Awareness Raising

- Provide targeted digital literacy training for groups like youth and the elderly. Equip individuals with tools to fact-check, verify sources, and evaluate online information critically.
- Encourage exposure to diverse, credible information sources to prevent the formation of echo chambers.

Science Communication

Transparency and Accessibility

- Train researchers to communicate complex topics clearly and responsibly, highlighting scientific uncertainty, ethical implications, and the self-correcting nature of science.
- Enhance public understanding of basic science by communicating its long-term potential and the value of foundational discoveries, even in the absence of immediate practical outcomes.

Tailored and Effective Communication Strategies

- Tailor science communication strategies to specific audiences based on demographics, culture, and trust levels, and use engaging formats such as storytelling, videos, infographics, and relatable success stories to improve accessibility.

Media Collaboration, Training and Community Engagement

- Train researchers to serve as science outreach ambassadors, who engage with schools and foster curiosity and public understanding from an early age.
- Encourage scientific communicators to participate in public outreach events (e.g., European Researchers' Night) to strengthen public engagement.
- Promote meaningful, two-way communication between scientists, civil society, local stakeholders, and the public, focusing on local needs, building trust, and using clear, respectful language that highlights the benefits of science.

Combatting Mis/Disinformation

- Develop proactive strategies leveraging trusted messengers to counteract mis/disinformation and conspiracy theories.
- Promote science and media literacy across society to enable critical assessment of information and engage with evidence-informed knowledge.

Building supportive policy frameworks

Develop Evidence-Informed Policies

- Develop coordinated strategies to identify and counteract the politicisation and strategic disinformation campaigns that undermine science, by partnering with independent media, civil society watchdogs, and academic experts in mis/disinformation.

- Integrate scientific evidence with ethical and societal considerations to ensure socially responsive policy making.

Ensure Political and Public Engagement

- Foster inclusive collaboration and mutual understanding between scientists, policymakers, and the public. Balance power dynamics among stakeholders and promote consensus-building approaches.
- Promote bottom-up approaches that empower citizens to support science education, advocate for evidence-informed policies, and hold decision-makers accountable.

Collaboration

Institutionalise and Strengthen Cross-Sector Collaboration

- Foster interdisciplinary, international, and cross-sector collaboration by creating multi-level platforms for knowledge exchange, best practice sharing, and policy development that actively involve policymakers, industry, educators, and civil society.
- Strengthen coordination both within and between policy makers, funders, scientific actors, and other relevant organisations, across departments, levels, and sectors, to overcome institutional silos and enable coherent policy implementation.
- Engage citizens in co-designing and evaluating research by addressing participation barriers, especially for marginalised groups such as those with lower educational attainment, economically vulnerable individuals, and older adults, and fostering inclusion through collaboration with local networks and community initiatives.

Enhance Collaboration through Mutual Understanding and Translation

- Encourage partnerships between industry, academia, and civil society to co-create science and align research with societal needs, ensuring transparency, accountability, and shared benefits.
- Create platforms for collaboration between Stewards of Trust, using innovative tools like games or story-writing, to share relatable narratives and foster mutual learning.

Foster Ethical and Open Research Practices

- Strengthen the culture of research ethics and integrity through inclusive collaboration between academic and non-academic stakeholders.

Leverage Influential Stakeholders

- Engage trusted public figures, including community and religious leaders, to strengthen credibility, broaden outreach and deepen public engagement with science.
- Strengthen ties between all Stewards of Trust and local communities and build effective connections across diverse stakeholder groups.

Adopt Sustainable Collaboration

- Foster collaboration among Stewards of Trust by creating incentives and mutual benefits that encourage long-term partnerships.

Science-Society Facilitators in the ecosystem of trust in science

Science-society facilitators play a vital role in democratising science, fostering mutual understanding, and empowering the public to actively contribute to research and innovation. By bridging the gap between scientific institutions and society, this domain can contribute to science transparency, relevance, and trust while expanding the scale and impact of research.

As illustrated below, these actors enhance science education by fostering understanding of the scientific process and supporting learning initiatives that empower citizens to engage meaningfully. They strengthen science communication through inclusive outreach strategies that build trust, promote dialogue, and inspire participation in research. In the policy domain, they help ensure science governance is shaped by public values, needs, and expectations, leading to more transparent and accountable decision-making. Their involvement in oversight processes brings attention to ethical and quality concerns in participatory research, helping refine standards and practices. By integrating citizen insights, they also support more context-sensitive and socially relevant implementation of scientific outcomes. In collaboration with funders and advocacy groups, they make the case for sustained investment in participatory models, ultimately helping to reshape science production into a more inclusive, democratic, and socially responsive endeavour.

Science-Society Facilitation and Citizen Science

References

Irwin, A. (2006). The politics of talk: Coming to terms with the 'new' scientific governance. *Social Studies of Science*, 36(2), 299–320.

Ottinger, G. (2013). Changing knowledge, local knowledge, and knowledge gaps: STS insights into procedural justice. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 38(2), 250–270.

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